

HISTORY OF THE IMPLEMENTATION PROCESS OF THE "COTTON WORK" REPRESSION POLICY IN GUZOR DISTRICT

Nurbek Suyarov

doctorant student of QarDu

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11096601>

Abstract. This article describes the repression of the "cotton work" carried out by the Soviet authorities in Uzbekistan and its consequences on the example of the fate of the people who suffered in Guzor district of Kashkadarya region.

Key words. Soviet power, repression, "Cotton case", detention center, Communist Party, "reconstruction", recession, T.Gdlyan, N.Ivanov, cotton dictatorship.

Guzor district, one of the main districts of Kashkadarya region, was established on September 29, 1926[5:2]. The area is 2.62 thousand km². In the district's agriculture, cotton, wheat, potatoes, fodder crops have been planted.

In the 80s of the 20th century, we can see that cotton was planted on the main part of the available land in Guzor district. During this period, as was the case throughout the republic, the population of Guzor district was not spared by the repressive policy such as the "cotton work". From people who are respected in the country to young people who have just started their careers, they became victims of this policy of repression. In particular, one of such cases is this - on October 12, 1985, the prosecutor's office of Kashkadarya region carried out preliminary investigations.

On September 2, 1986, a criminal case was initiated against Abrayev Bozor Arziyevich, who worked as a 2nd zone classifier at the cotton receiving point at the Guzor cotton ginning plant. According to him, Ravshan Muhammadiyev, the first secretary of the party committee of Guzor district, B. Abrayev, who worked as a 2nd zone classifier at the cotton center during the cotton harvest of 1981, Ural Ismailov, the director of the Guzor cotton ginning plant, It is written that it was found that the director of the Lenin state farm colluded with Khujam Norqabilov and others, abused his official authority for malicious purposes, and documented the delivery of cotton that was not actually grown and delivered at the "Lenin" state farm. [1: 34].

On December 3, 1986, this case was considered unilaterally in the court of Kashkadarya region. U. Ismailov, director of "Lenin" state farm, first secretary of the district party committee, told him that he instructed the deceased R. Muhammadiyev to add cotton. According to the court verdict, B. Abrayev will be deprived of freedom for 6 years. His property will be

confiscated and he will be banned from working in official positions for up to 3 years.

On December 20, 1991, the chairman of the presidium of the Supreme Court of Uzbekistan, A. Polvonzoda, took into account the protest, and B. Abrayev was suspended from action because there were no signs of a crime in his actions. Another criminal case considered in this district was recognized as a criminal case against Kochkinov Achil and others. This criminal case was initiated on March 12, 1986, as a result of the audit of the state farm named after Okhunboboyev, Guzor district, regarding the financial activities of the farm in 1982.

In 1982, at the state farm named after Okhunboboyev, Guzor district, director Kochkinov Achil, chief accountant Ernazarov Yoldosh, state farm cashier Artykov Koyli, Yusupov Khudoyberdi were working as a representative (sdatchik) at the cotton receiving point at the Guzor cotton ginning plant. directed at a group of people. Kuchkinov Ochil - born in 1916 in the city of Guzor, lived at 10 U. Nasir street. He worked as a director in the state farm named after Okhunboboyev, Guzor district. Ernazarov Yoldosh - was born in 1942 in the village of Tugal, Guzor district. He worked as a chief accountant in the state farm named Okhunboboyev, Guzor district. Artykov Quyli was born in 1946 in the village of Koshtepa. He worked as a cashier at the Okhunboboyev state farm in Guzor district. Yusupov Khudoyberdi was born in 1941 in the village of Koshtepa, Guzor district, and worked as a cotton delivery man at the state farm named after Okhunboboyev. [3:31].

In the indictment written by the prosecutor of Kashkadarya on April 8, 1986, Kochkinov Achil was the director of the Okhunboboyev state farm in Guzor district, and together with a group of officials of the state farm, he was found guilty of looting state property. A criminal case is initiated against them under Articles 119/1-m, 149/1-m, 153-m 2-q, 155 of the Criminal Code of the Uzbek SSR. The penalty of deprivation of liberty is used for different periods. When this case, which has not been fully investigated in all aspects, is brought back to the investigative process, it is recognized that there are no signs of a crime in the case.

The decision of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 22, 1991 basically cancels the verdict issued against the defendants in the case of A. Kochkinov and others[1:34]. Also, in another document related to the territory of Guzor district, it was determined that criminal case No. 7702 was initiated against Khasanov Erkin and others. On June 29, 1985,

court proceedings will be held on this criminal case. According to him, in 1982, in 1982, the director of the Drujba state farm of the Guzor district, Khasanov Erkin, the chief accountant Jalilov Faizullo, the cashier Boymirzayev Sunnatillo, and the representative of the state farm (sdatchik) Eshankulov Polatar at the cotton point of the district cotton ginning plant, using their powers, accusations such as falsification, preparation of forged documents and participation in bribery [2:227-265] are made. Khasanov Erkin - was born in 1947 in the village of Kamashi of Ulyanov district and lived there. At the time of his arrest, he worked as a chief agronomist in the Kashkadarya inter-farm animal husbandry office. Before this position, he worked as the director of the state farm "Druzhba" of Guzor district. E.Khasanov was sentenced to 8 years in prison by the judgment of the Kashkadarya Regional Court on May 28, 1986, and this period was determined to be spent in a labor colony under the enhanced order of correction. Measures for confiscation of existing property are determined.

Jalilov Faizulla was born in 1947 in the village of Yangikent, Guzor district. He worked as an auditor at Drujba farm in Guzor district. By the verdict of the Kashkadarya regional court on May 28, 1986, he was sentenced to 8 years of imprisonment, his property was confiscated. Boymirzayev Sanatullo was born in 1953 in Tashguzar village of Guzar district. He worked as an expeditor in the state farm "Druzhba" of Guzor region. S. Boymirzayev was sentenced to 7 years in prison and his property confiscated by the verdict of the Kashkadarya Regional Court dated May 28, 1986. By the verdict of the Kashkadarya regional court dated May 28, 1986, E. Khasanov, F. Jalilov were sentenced to 8 years in prison, S. Boymirzayev and M. Ismailov were sentenced to 7 years in prison. This term was set to be spent in a correctional labor colony in an extended manner. The presidium of the Supreme Court of Uzbekistan will consider this case from the point of view of justice. This case will be re-examined in the first years of independence, and when the evidence of the crime is not proven, the criminal case will be suspended. We witness that the cases examined by the investigators on the basis of this policy of repression were carried out hastily [4:54-67]. Most of the convicts are involved in investigative processes as innocent culprits.

So, in the 80s of the 20th century, the policy of repression was implemented in the entire Kashkadarya region, including in the Guzor district. Trials were carried out mainly against agricultural workers in this district. Among them, there were many accountants, economists, agronomists, foremen, and

employees of cotton centers, from the heads of collective farms and state farms. Thanks to independence, most of them were acquitted and the court sentences were annulled.

List of used literature:

1. ЎзМА, Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий суди ҳужжатлар тўплами. 1714-фонд, 10-рўйхат, 5334-йиғма жилд, 34-варақ.
2. Қашқадарё вилояти Суди, Жиноят ишлари бўйича судлов ҳайъати архиви. Хасанов Эркин ва бошқалар жиноят иши бўйича ҳужжатлар тўплами. 183-том. 227-265- варақлар.
3. Avliyaqulova D. Sovet hokimiyatining O'zbekistonning janubiy viloyatlaridagi qatag'on siyosati va uning oqibatlari (XX asrning 20-80-yillari). – Toshkent: Tafakkur, 2016. -B. 31.
4. Қашқадарё ВДА. Ғузор филиали. 1-фонд, 1-рўйхат, 1032-иш, 54—67-варақ.
5. Кашкадарьинская правда, 10 декабря. 1988 год.